

KELAYAKAN MEDIA VIDEO PEMBELAJARAN PADA SUBMATERI SISTEM ENDOKRIN

Agus Astuti¹, Ruqiah Ganda Putri Panjaitan², Titin³

^{1,2,3}Pendidikan Biologi, Universitas Tanjungpura

Jalan Prof. H. Hadari Nawawi, Bansir Laut, Pontianak, Kalimantan Barat

¹e-mail: agusastuti15@gmail.com

Submitted
2021-08-04

Accepted
2021-12-04

Published
2021-12-15

OPEN ACCESS

Abstrak

Penelitian bertujuan mengetahui kelayakan video sebagai media pembelajaran pada submateri Sistem Endokrin kelas XI SMA. Penelitian menggunakan metode penelitian deskriptif. Tahapan penelitian meliputi tahap penyusunan materi isi media video dan validasi media video. Validasi dilakukan oleh lima validator. Instrumen penelitian menggunakan lembar validasi. Penilaian lembar validasi menggunakan skala Likert. Aspek yang dinilai yaitu aspek format, isi, dan bahasa. Data dianalisis menggunakan formula Lawshe. Hasil validasi menunjukkan rata-rata CVR pada aspek penilaian format, isi, dan bahasa lebih besar dari batas minimum Lawshe. Berdasarkan hasil penelitian, maka disimpulkan bahwa media video dapat digunakan sebagai media pembelajaran pada submateri Sistem Endokrin pada kelas XI SMA.

Kata Kunci: kelayakan media; media pembelajaran; video pembelajaran.

Abstract

The research aimed to determine the feasibility of video as a learning medium in the Endocrine System submaterial in class XI senior high school. The research used descriptive method. The research stages include the stage of compiling the video media content material and the video media validation stage. Validation was carried out by five validators. The research instrument used a validation sheet. The validation sheet assessment used a Likert scale. The aspects that assessed were format, content, and language. Data were analyzed using Lawshe's formula. The validation results showed that the average CVR in the aspect of format, content, and language assessment was greater than the Lawshe minimum limit. Based on the results of the study, it can be concluded that video media can be used as a learning medium in the Endocrine System submaterial in class XI senior high school.

Keywords: media eligibility; learning media; tutorial video.